

Mission-context cross charting report

Deliverable No. 3.2

Douglas K. R. Robinson
30/06/2022

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101006382 - H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 / H2020-SwafS-2020-1

Executive Summary

This report presents the outcome of the MOSAIC cross-charting activity, which was centred on a two-day workshop as part of the First Annual meeting of MOSAIC, held in Paris on 24th and 25th February 2022.

The original objective of the cross-charting activity was to bring together the insights from Task 2.1 and 2.2 (the review of co-creation experiences in SwafS and elsewhere) and Task 3.1 (understanding the Mission implementation context) to define a selection of co-creation elements to integrate into the MOSAIC co-creation approach. In the first year of the MOSAIC project, based on the evolving timeline of the 5 Horizon Europe Mission Areas, an opportunity opened up for MOSAIC to align its work more closely to the Mission Areas. It was decided to strategically shift the overall MOSAIC plan from creating independent co-creation pilots to embedding in the mission “100 Climate neutral and Smart Cities by 2030”. Therefore, this added a third component to the cross-charting activity – the evolving timeline and implementation context of the “Cities Mission”.

This change in strategy towards embedding MOSAIC in the ongoing “Cities Mission” meant that it was impossible to define precisely what co-creation elements will be selected and taken forward – MOSAIC required room for manoeuvre and tailoring to be able to embed into the different activities of cities involved in the Cities Mission. We therefore focused on defining a number of MOSAIC co-creation design principles which would guide the co-development of MOSAIC co-creation activities with the cities that MOSAIC will work with over the coming 18 months.

With this shift in mind, the following report describes the cross-charting process and justification of the selection of co-creation principles that will guide the development of the MOSAIC co-creation approach in the Cities Mission context.

Deliverable Information

D3.2 – Mission-context cross charting report	
Deliverable number	3.2
Responsible partner	UNI EIFFEL
Due date of deliverable	31/03/2022
Actual submission date	30/06/2022
Version	1
Authors	Douglas K. R. Robinson
Reviewers	-
Work package number	3
Work package title	Understanding and co-designing projects for mission-oriented innovation
Work package leader	FGB

Dissemination Level		
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PP	Restricted to other programme participants, including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>

Nature of the Deliverable		
R	Report	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
D	Demonstrator	<input type="checkbox"/>
W	Website, patent filing, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>

0	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>
---	-------	--------------------------

Partners Involved in the Deliverable

Participant No.	Name of the Organisation	Short Name	Involved
3	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	UNI EIFFEL	X

Table of Contents

1. MOSAIC objectives and the cross-charting rationale	6
2. Three sources of insight into co-creation and the mission context.....	7
2.1 The Cities Mission state-of-play.....	7
2.2 Extracts of the insights from the Missions review.....	8
2.3 Extracts of the insights from the co-creation experience review	12
3. Ten guiding principles for MOSAIC co-creation.....	13
Principle 1: MOSAIC privileges prototypes and tangible mission contributions.....	13
Principle 2. Scalability of cocreation processes and outcomes is essential	13
Principle 3: Anticipating co-creation impacts as part of the co-creation process	14
Principle 4: Shared objectives and shared commitments	14
Principle 5: All quadruple helix actors must be present.....	14
Principle 6: Balanced representation of citizens and civil society organisations.....	15
Principle 7: Facilitate, support and build capacity for QH involvement.....	15
Principle 8: The values of all QH actors must remain in the whole "product lifecycle"	15
Principle 9: Be clear and honest regarding incentives and rewards	16
Principle 10: Don't reinvent the wheel	16
4. Conclusion	17
5. References.....	18
Appendix 1: Detailed Agenda of the 1st Annual Meeting of MOSAIC	19
Appendix 2: Workshop participants	23

1. MOSAIC objectives and the cross-charting rationale

Figure 1 represents the MOSAIC project aims to develop useful tools that can (a) draw on the experiences of the Science with and for Society (SwafS) programme regarding co-creation methods and processes, (b) tailor these based on new requirements related to the current drive in Horizon Europe for mission-oriented research and innovation, (c) harness the promise of quadruple helix based open innovation and (d) bring these insights together into a robust context sensitive co-creation approach.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the concepts on which the MOSAIC approach is based.

To be able to achieve this, from the outset, the MOSAIC project planned to cross-chart insights from an analysis of co-creation experiences in Europe (Deliverable 2.1) with the new context of mission-oriented research and innovation (Deliverable 3.1).

By Autumn 2021 (Month 10 of the MOSAIC project), the timeline of the five Horizon European Mission Areas was becoming clearer. Specific Missions were identified, and a baseline trajectory was outlined in the five mission Implementation Plans. To maximise impact of the MOSAIC project, as well as to get real-world feedback on the co-creation tools MOSAIC wished to develop, it was divided to strategically shift the overall MOSAIC plan from creating independent co-creation pilots to embedding in the mission “100 Climate neutral and Smart Cities by 2030”.

This change in strategy towards embedding MOSAIC in the ongoing “Cities Mission” meant that it was not pertinent to develop a co-creation approach *ex ante*, and then apply it in the Cities Mission — room for manoeuvre and tailoring would be necessary to co-develop the MOSAIC co-creation approach with the cities that MOSAIC will work within the CITIES Mission.

We therefore decided that the Mission cross-charting activity should aim, not to identify specific tools and approaches for the MOSAIC co-creation approach, but to focus on guiding principles that would aid the co-development of the co—creation approach with the pilot and replicator cities (see work package 4). Such principles, would build from the co-creation review (Deliverable 2.1), draw insights from the sense-making activity on Missions and their implementation contexts (Deliverable 3.1) and draw insights from the many MOSAIC engagements with cities and the Cities Mission that would occur as part of Task 3.4 and work package 5 activities between November 2021 and March 2022 (month 11 – 15 of the MOSAIC project).

This report presents the outcome of the MOSAIC cross-charting activity, which was centred on a 2-day workshop as part of the First Annual meeting of MOSAIC, held in Paris on 24th and 25th February 2022. Figure 2 shows the four elements that come together to inform the development of the MOSAIC co-creation guiding principles. The remainder of this report describes, in Section 3, some of the key

insights derived from Deliverable 2.1, Deliverable 3.1 and the embedding and engagement with the Cities Mission. Section 4 describes in brief the cross-charting workshop and presents the Ten Principles that will guide MOSAIC co-creation activities.

Figure 2: The elements that come together to inform the development of the MOSAIC co-creation guiding principles.

2. Three sources of insight into co-creation and the mission context

2.1 The Cities Mission state-of-play

Launched in September 2021 together with the four other EU Missions as part of Horizon Europe, the Cities Mission aims to achieve 100 climate-neutral and smart European cities by 2030. A key implementation mechanism at the heart of the Cities Mission is the Climate City Contract, which is framed as a new collaborative approach for reaching climate neutrality to be co-created with local stakeholders and citizens and will include climate commitments, an action plan and an investment plan. In terms of budget, Horizon Europe plans to invest around €350 million in research and innovation actions linked to the Cities Mission in the period 2021-23 with the ambition to mobilise funding from other programmes as well as attract private sector financing.

At the time of the cross-charting workshop, the Call for Expressions of Interest to join the Cities Mission, closed on 31 January, was being assessed with 377 cities from all EU Member States expressing an interest to become climate-neutral by 2030 as part of the mission.

A key player in the implementation of the Cities Mission, is the NetZeroCities Mission platform. Comprised of 33 partners from 13 countries, and running from October 2021-September 2025, the platform will support the delivery of the Horizon Europe Mission on 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030, providing technical, regulatory, financial and socio-economic expertise and assistance to cities in developing and implementing their CCCs and related investment plans. It was, therefore, important that the MOSAIC project remain aware of the Mission Platform activities and explore mechanisms for knowledge exchange.

Cities Mission

Figure 2: Cities Mission timeline (as of 24th February 2022)

The timeline, see figure 2, showed that mid-2022 will see both the final selection of the cities that will participate in the Cities Mission as well as the increased activity of the NetZeroCities platform. This provides a window of opportunity for MOSAIC to embed into the Cities Mission by working in-depth with two or three cities (as stated in the grant Agreement) as well as engaging more broadly with the cities through a Community of Practice, sharing insights on co-creation and other outcomes of MOSAIC activities.

2.2 Extracts of the insights from the Missions review

Whilst societal challenges may be considered as the broader social problem aim or benefit that is being sought (e.g., fighting climate change), “societal missions” represent a more narrowly defined set of activities that are supposed to deliver a verifiable result on a planned timescale that can be used to measure progress in overcoming the societal challenge.

In the past year, Horizon Europe has seen the launch of five missions that aim to drive, direct and orchestrate the European research and innovation ecosystem to provide solutions that can transform European society for the better. The European Missions have been designed to catalyse and drive large-scale transformations in key areas through ambitious and realistic game-changing solutions, that will provide public goods to Europe’s citizens. To be in line with the definition of societal missions, each mission articulates a clear, measurable and time-bound target, mobilising different stakeholders and actions around a common goal. The legal grounding of the European Missions can be found in the Horizon Europe Regulation, which outlines a set of criteria including that the “common goal” must be linked to an urgent societal challenge and also be relevant to a wide range of stakeholders from all parts of the quadruple helix.

Co-creation for missions differs from other forms of co-creation in that a clearly identified societal challenge has been articulated. This means that the outcomes of co-creation should contribute to the mission objective, in the case of MOSAIC, that is to contribute to one or more cities achieving climate neutrality by 2030.

In Deliverable 3.1 “Characterising Mission Implementation Contexts”, the concept of “missions” was reviewed both for the five European Missions, but also more broadly. Five insights from Deliverable 3.1, requirements for mission-focused co-creation, are relevant for this cross-charting exercise.

1. Given the short-time horizon for the five missions, that real impacts must be visible by 2030, requires that co-creation must lead to outcomes that can contribute to achieving the mission. Thus, for mission-focused co-creation, there is a particular need for co-creation that is designed to lead to tangible outcomes (observable changes) that will contribute to mission success.
2. Without a clear picture of how the outcomes of co-creation processes will contribute to the mission, it is unlikely that mission-focused co-creation processes will get the political support necessary or lead to desirable impacts. Thus, for mission-oriented co-creation, it is necessary to clearly articulate the “mission contribution” of the co-creation outcomes.
3. Because of the short-time frame for the five missions, traditional impact assessment approaches will not be useful for mission-focused co-creation. Therefore, anticipation of the legacy of co-creation, the pathways from co-creation to mission contribution, must be an essential part of any co-creation activity that is focused on contributing to a mission.
4. Whilst the impacts of the outcomes of co-creation cannot be measured in the life-time of the mission, good co-creation process can be measured. Therefore, metrics for measuring the quality of co-creation processes is needed, to ensure all voices are heard and to maximise the chance of achieving innovative and relevant solutions for the mission.
5. For sustainable citizen involvement, as well as building trust and “buy in” from civil society more broadly, it is essential that citizens, and other quadruple helix actors involved in co-creation, are appropriately rewarded and that the rewards are fairly distributed across the different parties involved in co-creation. Thus, it is essential that fair and equitable rewarding of participation in co-creation is an integral part of the design of co-creation activities and programmes.

Role of citizens diverse and not sufficiently framed in the mission discourse

Recalling the MOSAIC definition,

“Co-creation as Open Innovation (Co-innovation) is ‘a form of collaborative innovation, which is initiated by one or more members of the Quadruple Helix (a company, citizens or citizen group, research organisation or public agency), and involves contributors or co-creators from the other “helices” but above all from civil society to co-produce tangible outcomes, such as technologies, services or new organisational structures’.”

Citizens are at the heart of the MOSAIC co-creation definition and thus identifying how the five European Mission Areas frame the roles of citizens in achieving the mission’s objectives is important. Therefore, as part of Deliverable 3.1, which focused on reviewing the nature of missions and the 5 mission areas of Horizon Europe, it became clear that the term “co-creation” is rarely used in the official Horizon Europe documents on the Five missions. As we have discovered during our embedding in the Cities mission, and particularly the interviews with cities during their preparation of the “Expression of Interest”, the term “Citizen Engagement” is used as a loose umbrella term to capture all activities related to inclusion of citizens. Under this umbrella term, we can see that multiple citizen

roles are visible, stretching from citizens as co-innovators to citizens as data collectors to citizens as passive receivers of the outcomes of R&D.

In her report on implementing missions (Mazzucato 2019), Mariana Mazzucato, described roles for citizens in the design, implementation and evaluation of missions. To be able to position the MOSAIC co-creation approach(es) within the ongoing Cities Mission, and to be able to decide ourselves whether we position our co-creation as an element of citizen engagement (and empowerment), it is important to further clarify the different and diverse “framings”¹ of citizen roles in Horizon Europe missions.

What is the state of citizen roles in the current framing of the Missions? Is there an emphasis on a particular form of citizen involvement? Does this resonate with the MOSAIC definition of co-creation? Where can MOSAIC fit in to the current framing? And perhaps, where should MOSAIC be broadening the role of citizens via co-creation in the Cities Mission?

To this end, MOSAIC has built a draft citizen role framework, mobilising a number of taxonomies, consultancy reports and scientific articles (see Deliverable 3.1). This framework identifies a number of “roles” that citizens may play in the mission. The same citizen or citizen group can play multiple roles, thus the table provided below needn’t be mutually exclusive.

¹ “Framings” refers to how citizen’s roles are being described (or framed) by different stakeholders. In this way, framing is used to describe and designate a role to be played by a citizen. By unpicking such framings, we can reveal the biases and perspectives of those constructing Horizon Europe mission reports – which is clearly important because the documents under study are shaping and directing mission design and implementation!

Broad roles	Taxonomy of sub-roles	Description	Examples
Citizens as scientists	Data gatherer	Citizens capture and organise data through direct observation.	D-NOSES and odour monitoring in cities. Contributors in citizen science
	Interpreters and thinkers	Citizens synthesise and interpret data, from a variety of sources,	We Count, Cardiff citizens gathered and interpreted data (and its interpretation, to communicate issues to local authorities. https://we-count.net/news/cardiff-citizens-use-data-from-wecount-to-communicate-road-safety-concerns-to-local-councillors
	Problem setter and researcher	Citizens can take a lead role in defining and executing research, often, starting from a problem they encounter in their daily lives. Such activities can be done individually, in collectives and/or in collaboration with other actors.	La Paillasse, totally independent citizen led research. Lead amateurs in citizen science make use of fablabs and citizen science spaces, such as La Paillasse in the Gare du Nord region of Paris. https://lapaillasse.org/
Citizens as innovators	Tester	Citizens participate in the trialling and testing of new products, services and solutions, to better develop and hone innovations-in-the-making.	Beta testers for example in Living Labs, for example the Smart Mobility Living Lab. https://smartmobility.london/ . Another example is FAIRCHAIN, trialling Technological and social solutions for FAIRer dairy, fruit and vegetable value CHAINS
	Ideator and Designer	Citizens provide novel ideas and participate in design and co-design activities that can feed into the development of new products, services and practices.	Grenoble CivicLab (GCV) is an open challenge whose participants co-design and prototype projects which include a digital dimension and are of general interest for the citizens of the French region of Grenoble.
	Maker and Developer	Citizens produce their own products and further develop.	Users, makers, hackers and so on in Makerspaces, fablabs, etc. communities
	Diffuser and promoter	Citizens directly catalyse and drive the adoption and diffusion of innovations, particularly among specific user groups. They can act as educators, facilitating the generalisation and embedding of innovations.	The Open food facts platform was facilitated and promoted by citizens. .
Citizens as governors	Budget allocator	Citizens directly shape the targeting of spending, both actively by defining options for spending, and passively by choosing between options.	Participatory budgeting in Paris involves gathering ideas from citizens and then more broadly for citizens to select from those projects which should get financed. https://www.paris.fr/pages/budget-participatif-2021-comment-ca-marche-16525
	Policy definer	Citizens can be engaged in defining agenda for public action.	In France the NGO Agir tous pour la dignité (ATD) Quart monde successfully lobbied for the participation of “poor people” (concerned citizen) to governing agencies for inclusion in local policy definition.
	Jury member	Citizens can participate directly in decision making, evaluating and assessing innovations and their related impacts.	Citizen Assemblies. Citizen Juries, etc. etc.
Citizen as user and consumer	Individual consumer or user	Citizens can shape markets for innovations by selecting between options (when there are choices available).	Selecting between electric car or fossil-fuelled car, or public transport versus private transport.
	Critical user or consumer groups	Citizen as a member of a specific user group or consumer group.	Patient associations, local community collectives.
	Prosumers	Citizens play a hybrid role of both producing and consuming.	Digital online content and Urban agriculture initiatives.

2.3 Extracts of the insights from the co-creation experience review

The co-creation review, presented in Deliverable 2.1, provides insights into the range of co-creation rationales, tools and processes that may be mobilised for the MOSAIC mission-oriented co-creation approach. Looking at the selected SwafS projects reviewed in Deliverable 2.1, there are clear gaps, such as the lack of involvement of the full Quadruple Helix spectrum, lack of full-scale experiences in innovation settings and lack of clear tangible outcomes. However, one can take inspiration from the 50 projects reviewed, as outlined in the conclusion of D2.1, and paraphrased below.

Below, we briefly highlight a number of key insights (not exhaustive) that we have drawn from the co-creation review. For a more detailed account of the insights on co-creation tools, approaches and rationales, see Deliverable 2.1.²

What was visible in the co-creation review is that *building markets and reconfiguring value chains* is key to involving the private sector in Mission-oriented co-creation processes, as well as ensuring that the outcomes of co-creation will indeed contribute to mission objectives. In the discourse around Missions, businesses and industrial actors are seen as both sources of financing, sources of innovation capacities as well as key actors in the scaling of solutions. It is clear that industry actors can play multiple roles in mission-oriented co-creation (financing, novelty creation, scaling etc.), but what has not been clearly framed within the various co-creation activities analysed, as well as in the European Mission discourse, is the various motivations and incentives for integrating firms into co-creation.

Another key insight from the co-creation review is that there is a clear need for *promoting and increasing citizen inclusion*. As can be seen from the Table above, citizens can, and do play, multiple roles in research and innovation processes and are being framed in the Horizon Europe Mission texts in different ways (see Deliverable 3.1 for more details). For example, citizen science often contributes to *filling data gaps and creating open data through citizen mobilisation*, which can lead to a better, shared understanding of the challenges to address. Citizen science is one of the methods that can be used to support co-creation processes, however, a key aspect (often lacking in some of the reviewed examples) is that all stakeholders involved should have an active role in and benefit from all steps of the process.

As shown by several examples in the review, local aspects of co-creation processes are key to its successful implementation, and preparatory activities can be beneficial to identifying common ground and managing stakeholders' expectations. This means, that *building Quadruple Helix cohesion by harnessing territories and local resources* also represents an important step in co-creation. In a similar vein, *tapping unheard voices and the broader ecosystem of expertise* is also important for multiple reasons. The first is related to *Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)* where research and innovation processes should be inclusive – some stakeholders are rarely heard, and this undermines

² The 50 projects reviewed and described in detail in the annex of Deliverable 2.1, were mobilised as a resource in the cross-charting workshop, providing real source material for deep discussions on guiding principles for the MOSAIC co-creation approach.

the principles of RRI. The second, and particularly important for the Cities mission, is that all citizens may provide creative ideas and context-related knowledge that can be mobilised in co-creation activities. Thus, tapping into the diverse range of citizen groups, is key. Moreover, such processes should also always carefully plan ways of *incentivising participatory and inclusive innovation*, making sure that the co-developed solutions concretely benefit all actors involved in the process and their contributions are fairly recognised and rewarded.

3. Ten guiding principles for MOSAIC co-creation

During the cross-charting workshop, the three clusters of insights presented in the previous section were brought together and discussed. Starting with a series of working sessions on Thursday 24th February (See Appendix for workshop timetable and participant list) and culminating on Friday 25th in a morning brainstorm workshop (see figure 3), ten principles to guide the design and implementation of the MOSAIC co-creation approach were defined. In the following, each of the ten principles will be described.

Figure 3: The cross-charting workshop was held at the Université Gustave Eiffel, France, 24-25th May 2022

Principle 1: MOSAIC privileges prototypes and tangible mission contributions

Missions require transformative change that can only occur if there is a move from experimenting with co-creation approaches to driving towards concrete contributions to the mission aims. For MOSAIC, this means that any co-creation approach should lead to tangible outcomes. Ideally a prototype would be the focus of the MOSAIC co-creation approach, however, this cannot be guaranteed prior to the negotiation with the selected Cities piloting (and replicating) the MOSAIC approach.

Therefore, as a minimum, Principle 1 requires that clearly articulated tangible mission outcomes are the objective of all MOSAIC supported co-creation activities.

Principle 2. Scalability of cocreation processes and outcomes is essential

Without considering the scaling of the outcomes of co-creation processes, such activities are unlikely to lead to the transformative and behavioural changes required to achieve the Cities Mission. Scaling

is a clear gap in the SwafS co-creation activities reviewed in Deliverable 2.1, and thus the consideration of scaling should be integrated into the heart of the MOSAIC co-creation approach. Scaling for MOSAIC can be considered in two ways. **Scaling of outcomes**, is the move from prototype to full application of the co-created solution as well as its spread and growth in its application. **Scaling of processes**, is the spreading of good co-creation practice across city-centred innovation ecosystems.³ Taking seriously scaling of outcomes and processes requires also to take seriously the incentives to scale (see Principle 9). Credibility and legitimacy of co-creation outcome and processes is essential for scaling.

Therefore, any MOSAIC co-creation approach must be clear with regards to the scaling of outcomes of co-creation and the scaling of co-creation processes.

Principle 3: Anticipating co-creation impacts as part of the co-creation process

To improve the likelihood that the outcomes of co-creation will contribute to the mission aims, it is important to identify the pathways towards the mission-related impacts. Anticipation of the steps from the co-creation activity to the eventual contribution to transformative change in cities is essential. For MOSAIC, anticipation of the pathway to impacts allows the definition of indicators that can act as “criteria of success” to monitor and assess mission-oriented co-creation activities. It also can be used to identify the key actors that will carry the innovation forward (to identify the incentives and rewards to facilitate this journey – see Principle 9). It also can act as a means to articulate shared objectives by those who participate in the co-creation activity.

Therefore, any MOSAIC co-creation approach must include an anticipatory element which (a) articulates the desired contribution of the co-creation outcome to the Cities Mission aim and (b) articulates the path towards these mission-related contributions.

Principle 4: Shared objectives and shared commitments

Any MOSAIC co-creation will involve a variety of stakeholders in the co-creation exercise (see Principle 5). Since MOSAIC co-creation aims to create tangible outcomes that contribute to the Cities mission aims, any co-creation outcome must have a clear legacy and be carried forward by appropriate stakeholders. However, whilst it is clearly recognised that including a variety of stakeholders in the co-creation process leads to novel and robust solutions, what is not clear is the responsibility and accountability of those stakeholders that will carry the innovation forward.

Therefore, any MOSAIC co-creation approach must include processes to build shared objectives and clearly articulate commitments of the co-creation participants for both the co-creation activity itself and the next steps in the journey towards impact.

Principle 5: All quadruple helix actors must be present

A key element of Horizon2020, particularly in SwafS, was the focus on the benefits to be gained by bridging actors represented by the Quadruple Helix of science, policy, industry and society. Carayannis and Campbell define the Quadruple Helix as "Mode 3" Innovation ecosystem comprising of (1) Academia/Universities, (2) Industry/Business, (3) State/Government and a fourth helix (4)

³ The SwafS project SCALINGS explored the scaling of co-creation approaches and offers useful insights into the challenges and opportunities for scaling up and scaling out co-creation processes.

"media-based, culture-based and lifestyle-based publics" (Carayannis and Campbell 2009). More recently this fourth helix has been reformulated, for better or for worse, as "Civil Society". All four helices have a diversity of actors and motivations, but the key aspect is that for Open Innovation that is societally robust and relevant for the societal challenges of the day (represented in part, by the "Missions") unleashing the creative potential of the four helices through co-innovation is seen as key. Moreover, the different helix actors provide specific insights regarding the development, upscaling and use of innovation. In addition, it has been argued (Robinson et al. 2021) that interfacing the quadruple helices allows for democratising of innovation - a key element of the vision of Open innovation 2.0 (Moedas 2015).

Therefore, any MOSAIC co-creation approach should endeavour to include representatives from each of the four helices of Government, Industry, Academia and Civil Society

Principle 6: Balanced representation of citizens and civil society organisations

It is becoming increasingly recognised that co-creation activities that engage and integrate civil society (including local communities, non-governmental organisations and organised critical groups) provide clear added value - particularly the case for co-creation focusing on local issues and societal challenges (Kreiling and Paunov 2021). On the one hand civil society representatives can provide a user perspective in the design and development of an innovation - ensuring that the innovation is fit-for-purpose. Moreover, integrating civil society into the co-design and co-innovation aspects of co-creation can mobilise the creative potential inherent to the diversity of stakeholders that lie beneath the umbrella term of "civil society". In addition, for the transformative changes that are necessary to achieve the Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission, commitment from civil society with regards to behavioural change is also key - commitment goes hand in hand with trust and legitimacy of those activities that are aiming to provide solutions (such as co-creation activities).

Therefore, all MOSAIC co-creation activities must have a balanced representation of citizens and civil society organisations.

Principle 7: Facilitate, support and build capacity for QH involvement

Two key challenges can be observed regarding co-creation that has the ambition to include all quadruple helix representatives: (a) identifying relevant helix representatives is a major challenge and (b) having the capacity to integrate the different helices into a common activity. From the MOSAIC interviews with candidate cities for the Cities Mission, during December 2021 and January 2022, many of the cities described the challenge of "tapping unheard voices", particularly segments of civil society that are difficult to identify and to enrol in co-creation activities.

Therefore, every MOSAIC co-creation activity must facilitate, support and build capacity, for the cities involved in the Cities Mission, to effectively identify and integrate QH actors.

Principle 8: The values of all QH actors must remain in the whole "product lifecycle"

Mission-oriented co-creation implies that any co-creation activity must (a) lead to tangible solutions that can contribute to the Mission aims and (b) consider the journey from the co-creation activity to contribution to achieving the Mission (Principles 2 and 3). However, whilst all QH actors can be

involved in the co-creation activity, in the journey from co-creation to actual mission contribution, not all actors will be involved, certain actors will carry the innovation forward, scale it up and embed it into city ecosystems (cf. the Cities Mission). Since there will be an imbalance of “shaping power” over time between the QH actors, it is essential that the values of all QH actors in the co-creation activity are inscribed in the whole innovation journey from co-creation to Mission contribution – providing real incentives for participation (for example, from civil society). For the Cities Mission, cities that trigger co-creation should be supported in making sure that the co-creation activity itself allows these values to endure and that they are visible in the monitoring of the outcomes and impact of the co-creation activity.

Therefore, every MOSAIC co-creation activity must incorporate a means to (a) make explicit the values of each stakeholder group involved in the co-creation activity and (b) inscribe these values in the strategic agenda and monitoring mechanisms that cities will mobilise to evaluate progress from the co-creation activity to Mission contribution.

Principle 9: Be clear and honest regarding incentives and rewards

For effective co-creation involving representatives from different helices, it is important to be clear about the motivations and incentives of each partner that participate in co-creation. Moreover, at the heart of Responsible Research and Innovation, a fair and equitable rewarding of the different partners is key. For example, large criticisms have been made regarding the exploitation of grassroots initiatives and citizen science by innovation entrepreneurs, start-up impresarios and venture capitalists, depicted as ‘the public donating its unpaid work and data to privately owned, online entities’ and ‘extension of the sharing economy into the heart of scientific research’ (Mirowski P. 2017). Moreover, regarding representatives from the industry/business helix, as outlined in the “Characterising Mission Implementation Contexts” report (MOSAIC deliverable 3.1), the motivations and expected returns on investments differ across firms. For example, beyond monetary returns, motivations include opening up new markets, increasing the capacity to innovate and nurturing a firm’s embedding in its local community.

Therefore, Principle 9 states that all MOSAIC co-creation processes should always carefully plan ways of incentivising participatory and inclusive innovation, making sure that the co-developed solutions concretely benefit all actors involved in the process and their contributions are fairly recognised and rewarded.

Principle 10: Don't reinvent the wheel

The Co-creation Experience Review (MOSAIC Deliverable 2.1) has shown that many components of co-design and co-creation have already been trialled and tested, as can be seen with the 50 activities analysed. The review revealed clear gaps and needs for developing complementary co-creation components to enable Mission oriented co-creation in-line with the MOSAIC definition of co-creation.

Therefore, MOSAIC will mobilise existing and appropriate tools and processes as part of its co-creation approach, and only develop new co-creation tools and processes where there is a clear gap.

4. Conclusion

The ten guiding principles presented in this report combine insights from the Co-creation review (Deliverable 2.1), the Characterising Mission Implementation Contexts report (Deliverable 3.1), the MOSAIC consortiums interactions with candidate cities applying for the Cities Mission and the outcome of the 2-day workshop held as part of the 1st MOSAIC annual meeting (see appendix).

These principles articulate clear requirements for any MOSAIC co-creation approach whilst also allowing room for manoeuvre when co-developing co-creation activities with the selected Pilot Cities (see Work Package 4).

At the time of writing this deliverable, the ten principles have been presented at the WP4 Mutual Learning Workshop on the 24th May 2022 (see work package 4) and in part during the High-level Conference on Civic Engagement in EU Missions, organised by the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation in Paris, 21st March 2022 (See work package 5 for more details). For the latter, a number of MOSAIC partners presented the “Cities mission requirements” for co-creation and a number of challenges and opportunities going forward, highlighting some of the MOSAIC principles for co-creation (see Figure 3 below).

Figure 4: Douglas Robinson (UNI EIFFEL) and Marzia Mazzonetto (Stickydot) with Matthew Baldwin (Manager of the Cities Mission, Deputy Director-General of DG MOVE, European Commission) at the High-level Conference on Civic Engagement in EU Missions (21st March 2022, Paris).

5. References

- Carayannis, E. G., & Campbell, D. F. (2009). 'Mode 3' and 'Quadruple Helix': toward a 21st century fractal innovation ecosystem. *International journal of technology management*, 46(3-4), 201-234.
- Kreiling L. and Paunov, C. (2021) Knowledge co-creation in the 21st century: A cross-country experience based policy report. OECD Science, technology and Industry Policy papers. June 2021 No. 115DSTI/STP/TIP(2019)10/FINAL
- Macq, H., Parotte, C., & Delvenne, P. (2021). Exploring Frictions of Participatory Innovation between Sites and Scales. *Science as Culture*, 30(2), 161-171.
- Mazzucato M. (2019) Governing missions in the European Union. 2019. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/contact/documents/ec_rtd_mazzucato-report-issue2_072019.pdf
- Mirowski, P. (2017) Against citizen science. *Aeon Magazine*, Nov 2017. Retrievable here: <https://aeon.co/essays/is-grassroots-citizen-science-a-front-for-big-business>
- Moedas, C. (2015) Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World. Presented at the 'A new start for Europe: Opening up to an ERA of Innovation' Conference, June 22, Brussels.
- Robinson, D. K.R., Simone, A., & Mazzonetto, M. (2021). RRI legacies: co-creation for responsible, equitable and fair innovation in Horizon Europe. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 8(2), 209-216.

Appendix 1: Detailed Agenda of the 1st Annual Meeting of MOSAIC

Location: Room 101, Université Gustave Eiffel, France, 24th and 25th February 2022

Thursday 24th February

12h00 – 13h30 Lunch in the meeting room for those who come earlier

13h30 – 13h45 Welcome

13h45 – 15h30 **Critical eye on citizen roles in missions & co-creation tangible outcomes**
(UNI EIFFEL)

“Citizen-involved co-creation” captures broadly (and imperfectly) the MOSAIC definition of co-creation. However, in the various strategic documents of the five mission areas, co-creation is used loosely and rarely – the mission documents use “Citizen Engagement” as an umbrella term to capture all sorts of ways that citizens can engage in, and the roles they can play in, mission design, implementation and evaluation. It is therefore necessary for MOSAIC to have a landscape view of the way citizens roles are framed in the Horizon Europe missions.

Another element of the MOSAIC co-creation definition is that tangible outcomes are necessary for “good” co-creation. MOSAIC has reviewed 50 co-creation projects and thus, it is important to draw out what were/are the tangible outcomes, behavioural changes and legacies of the 50 projects. What can we learn from this? And what can we take forward into the design and execution of our own MOSAIC co-creation activities.

This session brings together two distinct themes that are important for designing and implementing MOSAIC co-creation within the Cities mission. We will cast a critical eye on:

- (a) citizen roles in the 5 Mission Areas, and particularly the Cities Mission
- (b) the tangible outcomes and legacies of the 50 co-creation projects that have been reviewed

Input:

- (1) A small note showing the first-round taxonomy of citizen roles in the 5 Mission areas key documents conducted by Douglas (*Reference Material 2.pdf*)
- (2) a small note showing the *very first* analysis of tangible outcomes conducted by Raphaël. (*Reference Material 1.pdf*)
- (3) The Annex of all 50 co-creation activity reports (*Reference Material 3.pdf*)

Objective: To (a) *identify* “in-roads” for MOSAIC forms of co-creation in the Missions framing of citizens engagements and to collectively *discuss* what is a desirable and interesting entrance point (or points) for MOSAIC and (b) discuss the thorny and often vague notion of tangible outcomes, drawing lessons from the 50 projects reviewed as inspiration (but not restricted to these projects alone).

Starting Questions:

- **Regarding citizens roles:** What is the state of citizen roles in the current framing of the Missions? Is there an emphasis on a particular form of citizen involvement? Does this resonate with the MOSAIC definition of co-creation? Where can MOSAIC fit in to the current framing? And perhaps, where should MOSAIC be broadening the role of citizens via co-creation in the Cities Mission?
- **Regarding tangible outcomes:** What can be considered as tangible outcomes? For the Cities mission (and other missions) citizen involvement and co-creation should contribute to the mission aim, and thus have a legacy through a variety of impacts (including behavioural change) – is this what we see? What are the dangers of “tokenism” in citizen engagement and co-creation? What could be MOSAIC requirements for our co-creation activities in this regard, to safeguard from tokenism and facilitate real “tangible outcomes”?

Envisioned endpoint:

- To have made a preliminary diagnosis of the range of citizen involvement that is visible in the Cities mission discourse and a reflection of how our original co-creation definition fits into this framing.
- To have decided what, for MOSAIC, is a tangible outcome and how this translates into design principles for MOSAIC co-creation.

By this point we should all be warmed up to dive into the Cities Mission discussion, having in mind the framings of citizen roles, MOSAICs interests in this regard as well as an idea of what we (MOSAIC) see as tangible outcomes – these factors may play a role in how we choose which cities to work with.

15h30 – 16h00 Coffee break

16h00 – 17h15 **Cities mission – where is it, what is foreseen and reflections on EoI interactions (SD and FGB)**

The session will:

- Provide a summary of work done with cities so far (call, webinars, support with EoI)
 - Present the cities that are interested on working with us (including feedback collected) – which ones do we select?
-

Input: A powerpoint presentation prepared by ERRIN to remind and update everyone on the on-going Cities Mission. (*Reference Material 4.pdf*)

Envisioned endpoint: A preliminary plan of our next steps in cities involvement towards **WP3 and WP4 activities**

17h15 – 18h00 **Planning of next steps in cities involvement towards WP5 activities: the MOSAIC community of practice and mutual learning activities (ERRIN)**

This session, a continuation of the previous session, will elaborate on the CoP and Mutual learning activities, based on our experience interacting and engaging with the cities over the past three months.

Envisioned endpoint:

A preliminary plan of our next steps in cities involvement towards **WP5 activities (CoL and Mutual learning)**

Friday 25th February

09h00 – 12h00 **Deliverable 3.2 working session: Cross Charting**

In the original MOSAIC proposal, we proposed a mechanistic combination of (a) the Co-creation Review findings and (b) the Mission Context review to identify which “mixes” of co-creation tools, processes and objectives would match the different needs of Missions. Since then, our focal mission, the Cities mission, has been launched and its evolved timeline has opened up a real window of opportunity for MOSAIC to embed into the Cities mission. This means we are moving away from a distantiated cross charting of the co-creation review and generic mission requirements, to now having the opportunity to embed our co-creation into actual mission activities – which of course means we will have to adapt and target our co-creation approach.

In this large session, we will focus on the broad design requirements for the MOSAIC co-creation approach. Whilst it is unclear precisely which city we will embed in, and also the nature of the co-creation activities we will be co-designing and co-implementing, we can define the broad principles of co-creation that we think are both appropriate to the Cities mission and that we think are relevant and of a suitable standard.

Building off Day 1 (citizen roles, tangible outcomes and cities mission realities) we will jump straight into the discussion of (a) what portfolio of principles

MOSAIC will use to (co-)design co-creation activities with the selected Cities and (b) tools, processes and approaches that could be mobilised.

Envisioned endpoint:

- To have made a list of principles that MOSAIC will mobilise when co-designing activities with cities, principles that are (a) in line with MOSAICs definition of co-creation, (b) relevant with regards to the Cities mission aims (and implementation agenda) and (c) in line with MOSAICs underlying values.⁴

(tbd)

20-minute Coffee break included in the previous session

12h00 – 12h45

WP6: updates and inspiring examples of impact assessment frameworks
(SoScience and Uni Eiffel)

WP6 has evolved with the repositioning of MOSAIC towards embedding, in real-time, in the Cities mission. It will be structured around two activities:

- (1) Building a self-evaluation tool to assess the quality of co-creation processes (in near-real-time)
- (2) Anticipating on mission contributions of co-creation activities and using this in the co-design of impact indicators (a key element of co-evaluation!)

The first approach will be led by SoScience building on the Biodiversa approach. The second approach will be led by UNI EIFFEL building on the ASIRPA Real-time methodology.

In this session both Biodiversa and ASIRPA Real-time will be presented.

12h45 – 13h45

Lunch

13h45 – 14h30

WP5 (ERRIN).

- Planning of strategic outreach activities
- Replication process (?)
- Planning of publications (led by SD and UNI EIFFEL)
-

14h30 - 15h00

Executive Board meeting (updates on amendment, budget)

⁴ This is a discussion point in itself. Should we make explicit MOSAICs underlying values: equitable, fair, responsible and accountable?

Appendix 2: Workshop participants

Institute	Name
ERRIN	Hilary Webb
ERRIN	Heidi Johansson
ERRIN	Ryan Titley
Fondazione Giannino Bassetti	Anna Pellizzone
Fondazione Giannino Bassetti	Cecilia Gaballo
Fondazione Giannino Bassetti	Angela Simone
LISIS - UNI EIFFEL	Raphael Stephens
LISIS - UNI EIFFEL	Mireille Matt
LISIS - UNI EIFFEL	Evelyne Lhoste
LISIS - UNI EIFFEL	Allison Loconto
LISIS - UNI EIFFEL	Douglas Robinson
SoScience	Melanie Marcel
SoScience	Lucie Van Nieuwenhuyze
SoScience	Roxane Bibard
StickyDot	Fabien Lambert
StickyDot	Maria Zolotonosa
StickyDot	Marzia Mazzonetto